

Transitions: Remembering the Past, Building the Future

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American astronomy without KPNO, CTIO, NOAO, and Gemini is hard to imagine. The contributions of our national observatories over 60 years have changed our culture, broadened our perspective, and provided opportunities for generations of astronomers. Through those 60 years, our national observatories have themselves changed and adapted to the evolving needs of our community.

My own engagement with KPNO and CTIO began in the late 1970s, while a postdoc at the University of Washington, working with the legendary George Wallerstein. Observing with the then-new echelle spectrographs on the Mayall and Blanco telescopes and at the coudé feed at Kitt Peak, collecting infrared photometry at the 50”, or PDS-ing plates at the downtown headquarters, I very much appreciated the support and help from observatory staff, most of whom became long-time friends and colleagues. Working at NOAO in the 1980s and 1990s showed me just how important the national observatories are to a thriving astronomical community, allowing any astronomer, anywhere, with a good idea to get the observations necessary to follow where that idea might lead. NOAO was a lively place, with a constant stream of visiting observers and

Dr. Catherine Pilachowski, seen working at the coude spectrograph, part of the KPNO 2.1m Telescope facility in the 1980s (left) and in 2005 (right).

researchers. Interactions on the mountaintops and at headquarters added to the vitality of the community, enabling many new collaborations and inspiring new ideas. Many young astronomers, myself included, benefitted from those interactions with more senior colleagues, as we took advantage of opportunities to learn from the great minds of that time.

Our national observatories also fostered community leadership, in a way that may be less commonly found in a university environment. The success of these observatories relies on teamwork, where different skills are required to achieve a larger, shared goal. So many of the postdocs and observatory staff who worked at NOAO and Gemini over the decades and then moved out into universities have become community leaders, and we have all benefited from their leadership.

The first visiting observer to Kitt Peak, back in 1958, was Arlo Landolt, renowned for establishing the fundamental standard stars for photoelectric photometry. Arlo was a graduate student at Indiana University at the time, and he has been a lifelong advocate for small telescopes available to the community. A key to the flowering of American astron-

omy in decades since 1958 has been the broad availability of telescopes big and small, allowing astronomy to grow not just at a few institutions with their own observatories but also at so many universities around the country.

Our national facilities have changed greatly since that time, as the needs of our community and the science we aspire to do have evolved. Today's NSF's NOIRLab resides in a very different world, providing access to data and data tools, organizing the community to take advantage of new resources, hosting the engines that produce major surveys, and providing clear and reliable pathways to Gemini, to Rubin, and eventually to the extremely large telescopes of the twenty-first century. Our community is strengthened as our national facilities are brought together under the new umbrella of NOIRLab. America's leadership in ground-based OIR astronomy in the world in the twentieth century owes much to the vision of the founders of our first national observatory 60 years ago. Our leadership in the twenty-first century will depend on the combined strength of our national observatories together with our flagship independent observatories—a formidable partnership as we learn to work together.